

Article

Acylphosphates as versatile transient species in reaction networks and optical catalyst screenings

In this work, we introduce an exceptionally robust, versatile, and catalytically tunable organophosphate/acylphosphate reaction cycle and demonstrate emergent behavior such as transient aggregation and excimer formation. In addition, we exploit the transient fluorescent properties of acylphosphate-bridged excimers for rapid catalyst screenings that could become a general tool in systems chemistry. The broad substrate scope, distinct kinetics, and ability to retain negatively charged steady-state species make acylphosphates highly attractive for the creation of transient self-assemblies and molecular machines.

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Highlights

An acylphosphate-based reaction cycle is introduced

Non-equilibrium steady states are harnessed for transient excimer formation

Transient excimers enable optical catalyst screenings

Article

Acylphosphates as versatile transient species in reaction networks and optical catalyst screenings

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SUMMARY

Chemically driven reaction cycles are prevalent in nature; yet, artificial examples are still rare and often lack robustness or versatility. In this study, we introduce acylphosphate steady states that can be accessed from a wide range of organophosphates using either carboxylic anhydride or carbodiimide fuels. The combination of carboxylic anhydride fuel and pyridine catalysis makes this chemistry sufficiently robust to allow for 25 fueling cycles without generation of observable quantities of detrimental side products such as pyrophosphates. We demonstrate that the acylation of organophosphates gives rise to transient aggregates, and we harness the transient fluorescence of acylphosphate-bridged excimers in rapid screenings of more than 50 catalysts in a single well plate experiment. Due to its versatility and robustness, we anticipate that the organophosphate/acylphosphate reaction cycle will prove useful for the creation of chemically driven molecular machines and transient self-assemblies.

INTRODUCTION

Non-equilibrium steady states underpin a large number of essential cellular processes. Examples range from the dissipative self-assembly of actin filaments¹ and microtubules² to the directed mechanical motion found in motor proteins.³ In all of these examples, nature uses enzyme catalysis and the availability or the lack of chemical fuel to enable spatial and temporal control over nontrivial functions (e.g., directed transport, mitosis, and muscle contraction). To create artificial non-equilibrium steady states in the lab, typically an equilibrium between two well-defined chemical species is coupled with an exergonic process in such a way that the components of the reaction cycle act as catalysts for the transformation of a chemical fuel⁴ into waste.^{5,6} Several fuel classes and building blocks for the design of artificial reaction cycles have been investigated. A first example by van Esch and coworkers explored a methyl iodide-driven reaction cycle that was used to induce the transient gelation of aryl esters.⁷ More recent studies focused on other fuels including agents for acylation,^{8,9} methylation,^{10–12} and oxidation,^{13–17} as well as triphosphates,^{18–20} sugars,^{21,22} decarboxylating acids,^{23–26} and carbodiimides.^{27–32} In particular, carbodiimide-driven reaction cycles, which rely on the transient formation of carboxylic anhydrides and esters, attained popularity in non-enzymatic systems chemistry (Figure 1A).³³ Despite drawbacks related to *N*-acyl rearrangements and the problematic accumulation of urea waste products (H bond donor and acceptor), carbodiimides are excellent fuels because they exhibit only minor background hydrolysis and therefore allow efficient and reliable control of reaction cycle steady states.³⁴ On this basis, impressive feedback effects³⁵ and the coupling of two reaction cycles in a thermodynamic cascade were developed.³⁶ Supramolecular

THE BIGGER PICTURE

More than six decades ago, Richard Feynman was fascinated by the ability of cells to “walk around,” “wiggle,” and “do all kinds of marvelous things.” We now know that this behavior is facilitated by motor proteins that transform chemical energy into mechanical motion. Key for the efficient operation of these machines is that they act as catalysts for the hydrolysis of ATP (or GTP) fuel. Scientists have only recently been able to create artificial Brownian ratchets that can autonomously transform chemical fuels into directed motion. However, the underlying chemical reaction cycles have been limited to carboxylic esters and anhydrides. The work described herein expands the toolbox of molecular machinists and systems chemists by the addition of an acylphosphate reaction cycle that is exceptionally robust and based on negatively charged building blocks that should be ideally suited for embedding molecular machines within lipid bilayer membranes.

Figure 1. Overview of state-of-the-art and present work

For a Figure360 author presentation of this figure, see <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chempr.2023.11.015>.

(A) State-of-the-art: relevant examples for chemically driven, non-enzymatic reaction cycles. (B) This work: scope, methodology, and advantages of the organophosphate/acylphosphate reaction cycle.

assemblies, such as vesicles,³⁷ microdroplets,³⁸ and cryptands,³⁹ could be generated in a transient, carbodiimide-driven manner as well. However, compared with nature, where enzyme catalysis is used to assert kinetic control over the hydrolysis of otherwise inert phosphoanhydrides, few studies on artificial reaction cycles focus on catalytic control. Pioneering work by Eelkema and coworkers demonstrated how organocatalysis can be used in a beneficial way to tune the kinetics of a carboxylic ester reaction cycle.⁸ We previously reported a phosphoramidate reaction cycle that exhibited exceptional kinetic control afforded by the use of 1-ethylimidazole as an organocatalyst.⁴⁰ Also, Leigh and coworkers recently showcased how chiral organocatalysts can be applied within an carboxylic anhydride reaction cycle to induce a directionally biased rotation around a C–N single bond.⁴¹

The design of life-like systems is also highly relevant to prebiotic chemistry and especially to the question how a possible “RNA world” arose.^{42–45} A compound class, which was recently identified to be potentially of prebiotic importance, are acylphosphates.^{46,47} Specifically, these mixed phosphorus/carbon-anhydrides were applied in non-enzymatic oligoribonucleotide ligations⁴⁸ as prebiotic phosphorylation and acylation agents^{49–51} and as aminoacyl precursors to drive peptide formation.^{52,53} Moreover, acylphosphates hold a prominent role in nature because they serve as vital intermediates in numerous biological processes. Their significance becomes evident in various metabolic pathways, including glycolysis⁵⁴ and pyruvate metabolism.⁵⁵ Moreover, acylphosphates in the form of tRNAs are indispensable in protein biosynthesis.⁵⁶ In light of this background, and because methods for the non-enzymatic formation and for the hydrolysis of acylphosphate have been reported,^{57–61} we wondered whether the two reactions could be combined under mild, preferably organocatalyzed conditions to furnish a new type of reaction cycle.

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Herein, we report on acylphosphates as highly versatile transient species in chemically driven reaction networks (Figure 1B). In proof-of-principle experiments, we demonstrate that non-equilibrium steady states from acylphosphates can give rise to transient aggregation and to the transient formation of excimers. We describe the wide scope of substrates and fuels, and we propose methodology that streamlines the search for efficient hydrolysis catalysts (optical well plate screenings).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Exploration of acylphosphate formation

Acylphosphates are known to undergo hydrolysis in aqueous medium,⁶² establishing an equilibrium that is shifted by several orders of magnitude toward the respective phosphate and carboxylate species. Chemically driving such a system to a non-equilibrium steady state requires high-energy reagents that react preferentially with organophosphates rather than directly with water, which potentially requires suitable catalysts. Our development of a chemically driven acylphosphate reaction cycle, therefore, started with an investigation of acylation methods that are in principle feasible in dilute aqueous buffer. To ensure comparability of results, we initially focused on the acetylation of 1-naphthylphosphate (NaphPO₄). The concentrations of the substrate and the acetylated product were determined by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) using an internal standard.

Table 1 depicts the highest activation yields observed within 90 min for different acetylation agents in the presence and absence of pyridine. Direct acetylation agents (entries 1–8) were examined first. Nearly all methods resulted in the formation of at least a limited amount of naphthalene-1-acetylphosphate (NaphAcPO₄); yet, the nature of the acetylation agent is crucial for the efficiency of the process. The observed differences can be explained by the relative reactivity and the hydrolytic stability of the acylation agents. Among the reagents shown, acetyl chloride (entries 1 and 2) exhibits the highest reactivity and undergoes rapid nucleophilic substitution with a variety of nucleophiles, including water.

Background hydrolysis is therefore too fast in the case of acetyl chloride, even if pyridine was added in an attempt to favor the acylation reaction over hydrolysis via nucleophilic catalysis (entry 2).⁶³ By contrast, less reactive acetic anhydride gave rise to 38% NaphAcPO₄ (entry 3) and to nearly quantitative conversion in the presence of pyridine (entry 4). We determined that around 66% of the anhydride is converted to the respective acylphosphate, indicating a surprisingly good fuel-to-waste efficiency of the chemical reaction cycle (Table S6). NHS-esters (entries 5 and 6) represent another class of acylation agents that are commonly used in aqueous environments⁶⁴ and exhibit a higher tolerance against hydrolysis when compared with carboxylic anhydrides. Conversion to NaphAcPO₄, turned out to be quite low, however, indicating that acetic anhydride resembles a good balance of reactivity and background hydrolysis, at least for the investigated reference system. Two transacetylation experiments were conducted using acetylphosphate (entries 7 and 8), yet, without noticeable conversion, which is not too surprising, because the hydrolysis half-life of NaphAcPO₄ is lower compared with that of acetylphosphate (Figures S67 and S72). Remarkably, the introduction of pyridine consistently led to enhanced activation yields, underscoring the importance of organocatalysis. Other pyridine derivatives and various Lewis base catalysts were also explored and investigated within the reaction network. As can be seen in Figure S3 and Table S3, the majority of catalysts resulted in enhanced activation yields, notably with electron-deficient pyridine derivative as the most efficient ones.

Table 1. Categorical comparison of acylation methods for naphthyl-1-phosphate

Entry	pH	Acylation agent	Catalyst	Activation yield (%)
1	7.5		none	3
2	7.5		pyridine	12
3	7.5		none	38
4	7.5		pyridine	97
5	7.5		none	1
6	7.5		pyridine	6
7	7.5		none	0
8	7.5		pyridine	0
9	7.5		none	20
10	7.5		pyridine	40
11	5.5		none	47
12	5.5	+ EDC	pyridine	81

Reaction conditions: naphthyl-1-phosphate (25 mM), MOPS or MES buffer (250 mM), 4 equiv of acylation agent, naphthyl-2-sulfonate as internal standard (12.5 mM), pyridine (200 mM), water as solvent.

We proceeded to investigate the indirect acylation of **NaphPO₄** with a combination of acetic acid and a secondary activation agent. Carbodiimides are arguably the most popular reagents for carboxylic acid activation and are frequently used in carboxylic anhydride- and ester-based reaction cycles.³³ Thus, we tested a 1:1 admixture of acetic acid and 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide (EDC) at pH 7.5 and 5.5. (entries 9–12.) The presence of pyridine significantly enhanced the acetylation and led to activation yields up to 81% (entry 12). The experiments were conducted in a more acidic environment (i.e., pH 5.5; entries 11 and 12) because EDC activation is more effective under these conditions.⁶⁵ Other indirect acylation agents such as *N,N,N',N'*-tetramethyl-*O*-(*N*-succinimidyl)uronium hexafluorophosphate (HSTU) and di-2-pyridyldithiocarbonate (DPDTC) were also investigated yet were found to be less effective than EDC (Table S2). Overall, the results obtained with acetic anhydride and EDC provide an ideal starting point for establishing an organophosphate/acylphosphate reaction cycle.

Optimization of system parameters and cycling experiments

Having gained preliminary insights into efficient acylation methods and the effect of nucleophilic catalysis, we shifted our attention toward the optimization of reaction parameters affecting the entire **NaphPO₄/NaphAcPO₄** reaction cycle (Figure 2A). Our objective was to gain a more detailed understanding and control of the system parameters. One of the most important parameters appeared to be the concentration of pyridine, which is why we monitored the system composition over time upon

Figure 2. Optimization of NaphPO_4 reaction network

(A) Reaction scheme of NaphPO_4 -based reaction cycle. (B) Influence of pyridine on Ac_2O -driven cycles. The determination of half-lives in the presence of pyridine was achieved by fitting the exponential decay. The dotted line serves as a visual guide. (C and D) Four consecutive fuel additions in Ac_2O /EDC-driven reaction cycles. The concentrations of NaphAcPO_4 (red) and NaphPO_4 (blue) were determined in triplicate using quantitative HPLC. Data points are connected to guide the eye; whereas error bars represent the standard deviation. Reaction conditions: naphthyl-1-phosphate (25 mM), aqueous MES or MOPS buffer (1 or 2.5 M), 4 equiv of acylation agent per cycle, naphthyl-2-sulfonate as internal standard (12.5 mM), pyridine (200 mM). (E) Investigation of 25 consecutive fueling cycles. Conversion of NaphPO_4 to NaphAcPO_4 was determined 20–30 s (for Ac_2O) and 2–3 min (for EDC) after fuel addition. Refueling was performed after 90% of NaphAcPO_4 was hydrolyzed back to NaphPO_4 . Reaction conditions: naphthyl-1-phosphate (25 mM), naphthyl-2-sulfonate as internal standard (12.5 mM), pyridine (750 mM), MOPS (1 and 2.5 M), or acetate buffer (1 M), 3 equiv of fuel (EDC shown in blue or Ac_2O shown in brown and gray), $T = 25^\circ\text{C}$ and $\text{pH} = 5.5$ for EDC and $\text{pH} = 7.5$ for Ac_2O fueling. In case of Ac_2O as fuel 6 equiv of NaOH was also added after every cycle (gray data) to prevent a drift of pH. Error bars represent the standard deviation (triplicate execution).

addition of 4 equiv of acetic anhydride (Figure 2B). As expected, we found that the pyridine concentration had a positive effect on acylphosphate formation, and only a maximum yield of 38% for NaphAcPO_4 was observed in the absence of pyridine. As

becomes evident from [Figure 2B](#), pyridine also has a strong effect on hydrolysis rates, which can be attributed to the fact that the acetylated pyridinium species^{60,62,66} plays a central role in both the acyl phosphate formation and its hydrolysis (as illustrated in [Scheme S1](#)). This finding highlights an evident advantage of a reaction cycle that is subject to (organo)catalysis, namely, that the hydrolysis half-life of the transient acylphosphate can be fine-tuned from mere minutes to several hours, solely by varying the pyridine concentration. Pyridine catalysis also enables the generation of steady-state mixtures under mild conditions, such as room temperature and neutral pH. Other parameters, including fuel equivalents, precursor concentration, temperature, and pH, were found to also affect the kinetics of the two reactions forming the reaction cycle and are depicted in more detail in the supplemental information ([Tables S4](#) and [S5](#); [Figure S4](#)). In this context, it is worth noting that the system is robust across a broad range of parameters (even at elevated temperatures and from moderately acidic to alkaline conditions).

The system's behavior upon refueling was studied by monitoring the concentration of NaphPO_4 and NaphAcPO_4 during sequential additions of either acetic anhydride or EDC ([Figures 2C](#) and [2D](#)). Whereas the acetic anhydride driven reaction cycle reached its NaphAcPO_4 peak concentration within a few seconds, the EDC-driven system required several minutes. As can also be seen from [Table 1](#) (entry 12), the activation yield in the case of EDC was slightly lower compared with acetic anhydride. This can be attributed to a slower forward reaction, which is likely due to the additional elemental step of acid activation that makes hydrolysis (more) competitive. The hydrolysis kinetics are almost superimposable in both cases, indicating the exceptional robustness of this reaction cycle. Specifically, we found that the organophosphate NaphPO_4 was fully regenerated, and no signs of pyrophosphate—as a kinetically inert side product resulting from activation of phosphorus^{40,67–69} rather than carbon—were detected by HPLC or ^{31}P -NMR spectroscopy ([Figures S5](#) and [S6](#)). Regarding the issue of waste buildup, both the direct and indirect activation strategies have advantages and disadvantages. On the one hand, the use of acetic anhydride is essentially free of side products yet leads to a decrease in pH due to the release of acetic acid as a waste product. This buildup of acetic acid could potentially cause issues when performing a large number of cycles, unless it is neutralized with a base or by the presence of highly concentrated buffer systems. On the other hand, addition of EDC hydrochloride does not alter the pH of the system significantly but leads to *N*-acylurea byproducts³⁴ and to 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethyl-aminopropyl)urea (EDU) as a terminal waste product (acetic acid is recycled in this activation mode). EDU is a strong H bond donor and H bond acceptor, and it is therefore far from innocent if transient self-assembly is the desired emergent property at steady state. As shown in [Figure 2E](#) (blue data), we were able to use EDC as fuel over 25 cycles without any noticeable fatigue of the system. When using acetic anhydride as fuel, 2 equiv of acetic acid for each equiv of fuel are generated during each cycle as waste. In this case, the system shows noticeable fatigue over 25 cycles ([Figure 2E](#), red data). More well-behaved data over 25 cycles could be obtained, if NaOH was added after every fifth ([Figure S7](#)) or after each cycle (gray data in [Figure 2E](#)).

Transient aggregation and excimer emission of pyrene-bridged acylphosphates

Having largely understood the $\text{NaphPO}_4/\text{NaphAcPO}_4$ reaction cycle, we sought to explore functional aspects of chemically driven acylphosphate steady states. For this reason, we turned our attention to the transient acylation of pyrene-1-phosphate (PyrPO_4). The extended π -system in PyrPO_4 leads to increased lipophilicity

Figure 3. Fluorescence change in Pyr_2AcP non-equilibrium steady states

(A) Reaction scheme behind $\text{PyrPO}_4/\text{Pyr}_2\text{AcP}$ reaction cycle.

(B) Fluorescence spectra showing varying $\text{PyrPO}_4/\text{Pyr}_2\text{AcP}$ non-equilibrium steady states upon addition of EDC to PyrPO_4 (20 mM) and adipic acid (15 mM).

(C) Photoluminescence spectra during four consecutive cycles before and 60 min after fuel addition. $I_{\max}^{\text{exc}}/I_{\max}^{\text{mon}}$ presents the ratio between the intensities observed for maximal excimer and monomer emission (at 485 and 405 nm, respectively). Reaction conditions: 20 mM PyrPO_4 , 15 mM adipic acid, 100 mM EDC, 1 M MOPS buffer, $T = 25^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{pH} = 6.5$, $\text{H}_2\text{O}:\text{DMF}$ (1:1). error bars represent the standard deviation of triplicate experiments.

and stronger intermolecular (i.e., π - π) interactions such that the charge reduction⁷⁰ during anhydride- and/or carbodiimide-fueled acetylation results in transient aggregation and phase separation of the respective product (Figures S8 and S9; Videos S1 and S2). The system could successfully be refueled for four times by the consecutive addition of 4 equiv of fuel. Compared with NaphAcPO_4 , which would hydrolyze within minutes under the standard conditions applied here (Figure S4), it is remarkable that the turbidity caused by pyrene-1-acetylphosphate (PyrAcPO_4) lasts for several hours, which could be indicative of aggregation induced negative feedback and exemplifies the utility of acylphosphate for fueled self-assemblies.^{38,71}

Because chemically driven self-assemblies are increasingly well established,^{72–75} and only few examples have been reported on transient changes in optical properties,^{12,76–82} we decided to pursue unique opportunities that pyrenes such as PyrPO_4 present in the latter arena. By employing the reaction cycle depicted in Figure 3A, we were able to establish chemically driven excimer emission. PyrPO_4 and adipic acid were used as substrates in mixed aqueous solvent ($\text{H}_2\text{O}:\text{DMF}$ 1:1), and EDC was added as a fuel to facilitate the 2-fold phosphorylation of the diacid. The resulting product Pyr_2AcP possesses two covalently linked pyrene moieties and displays a red-shifted fluorescence compared with the respective monomer emission. The

origin of this spectral shift can be attributed to the formation of excimers, i.e., the intramolecular interaction between two pyrene moieties.

As shown in [Figure 3C](#), we exposed this system four times to EDC fuel and monitored the emission spectra. At equilibrium, i.e., at the beginning and the end of each fuel cycle, the system exhibited near-ultra-violet fluorescence between 375 and 450 nm, which is characteristic for the pyrene monomer. However, shortly after EDC addition, the fluorescence of the solution shifted bathochromically to sky-blue, indicating that the Pyr_2AcP excimer is dominant at steady state ([Figure S12](#); [Video S3](#)). Dimers or oligomers from adipic acid were not observed (HPLC-mass spectrometry [MS]). Excimer emission reached its maximum after ca. 40–60 min, represented by the broad band at around 485 nm in the fluorescence spectra of [Figures 3B](#) and [S10](#). This transient behavior is also reflected in the photoluminescence quantum yield (21%–23% after 60 min and 9%–11% before fuel addition, when excited at 340 nm) of the system that is continuously and predictably changing over time upon addition of the fuel ([Figure S11](#)). Over the four investigated cycles, we found that the ratio of excimer emission ($I_{\text{max}}^{\text{exc}}$) to monomer emission ($I_{\text{max}}^{\text{mon}}$) is almost invariant, see inset in the upper right corner of [Figure 3C](#). Leaving aside the aforementioned issues with N-acylurea byproducts,⁸³ this good reproducibility upon refueling showcases that the acylphosphate reaction cycle is not only robust but also highly versatile in respect to different types of emergent behavior.

Optical screening of hydrolysis catalysts

Having developed a system that exhibits distinct fluorescent properties at equilibrium and at the fuel-driven steady state, it occurred to us that transient excimers, such as Pyr_2AcP , could be of value for the advancement of systems chemistry. Although optical readouts have been developed for biochemical investigations,^{84,85} parallel well plate screenings to report on the chemical state of a large number of chemical reaction networks are unexplored. For this reason, we isolated Pyr_2AcP and used its transient excimer emission in an optical screening setup. In the context of this study, the following experiments served the purpose to identify further catalysts for acylphosphate hydrolysis and thus gain a broader control over acylphosphate steady-state kinetics ([Figure 4A](#)). Specifically, we loaded a 96-position well plate with Pyr_2AcP , as well as a wide range of catalysts, and monitored the fluorescence intensity of the excimer (at 500 nm) by the aid of a microplate reader. Because excimer emission is a specific property of the transient dimeric species, the fluorescence signal at 500 nm gradually decreases while the concentration of Pyr_2AcP diminishes. It is worth emphasizing that using a fluorescence-based response for this purpose offers two significant advantages. First, these measurements can be carried out in highly diluted media, which means that only minimal amounts of reactants are required for initial assessment. Second, and perhaps more importantly, when using a well plate setup, a large number of reactions can be monitored rapidly and continuously, because it only takes a few seconds (depending on the instrument; in our case 20 s) to scan the entire well plate (at 500 nm). In comparison with conventional analytical techniques commonly employed in systems chemistry, such as HPLC and NMR, where a single measurement of one sample can take several minutes, a microplate reader allows measurements of the fluorescence intensity in dozens of samples within a few seconds.

As shown in [Figure 4A](#), our well plate design included over 50 compounds that can be evaluated as potential hydrolysis catalysts with a total effort amounting to only 1 day of labor for one person. Following the promising results obtained with pyridine in fine-tuning the simpler $\text{NaphPO}_4/\text{NaphAcPO}_4$ reaction cycle, this microwell plate study focused on further Lewis bases, such as pyridine derivatives, imidazoles, unsaturated nitrogen-containing heterocycles, oximes, succinimides, and phosphines. Furthermore,

A Hydrolysis induced fluorescence change

investigated catalysts and wellplate positions

B Catalyst heatmap

C Fluorescence time progression

D Catalyst champion table

entry	catalyst	structure	wellplate position	half-life [min]
1	DMAP		A1	1.5
2	Purine		C8	1.8
3	3,4-Lutidine		A2	2.4
4	4-Methoxypyridine		A3	2.7
5	1-Propylimidazole		B3	5.0
6	1-Ethylimidazole		B4	7.1
7	4-Methylimidazole		B6	7.7
8	1-Methylimidazole		B5	8.0
9	4-Picoline		A4	8.8
10	Imidazole		B7	9.0

Figure 4. Utilizing transient fluorescence of excimer species

(A) Reaction scheme of Pyr_2AcP hydrolysis and general structures of catalysts used in well plate design.

(B) Heatmap of relative fluorescence decay for all catalysts over 120 min. Catalysts are sorted according to the fastest fluorescence decay within their respective catalyst class.

(C) Heatmap of fluorescence decay in the presence of various catalysts after 20 and 2,000 min.

(D) Table of the ten best catalysts sorted according to the shortest half-lives of fluorescence decay. Reaction conditions: $6 \mu M Pyr_2AcP$, 10 mM catalyst, 250 mM MOPS buffer, pH = 7.5, T = 25°C. Note: experiments with lanthanoid salts were conducted at pH 5.5 with 250 mM MES buffer for solubility reasons.

Lewis acids, such as transition metals and lanthanoid salts, were included as well. A qualitative overview of the observed hydrolysis performances can be gained from the depicted heatmaps and the respective color code (Figures 4B and 4C). Dark color indicates a high fluorescence intensity at 500 nm and thus a low amount of hydrolysis at this given time, whereas a bright color indicates the opposite. From the heatmap representing 20 min reaction time, it is evident that, in some experiments, hydrolysis had already gone to completion, indicating efficient catalysis (for reference see Table S8: $t_{1/2}$ [pyridine] = 107 min and $t_{1/2}$ [no catalyst] = 895 min). The entire time course of fluorescence

decay is also depicted in the heatmap shown in [Figure 4B](#). It is important to mention that the nature of the catalyst can also affect the optical properties of the system (e.g., due to quenching). As a result, the initial fluorescence of specific catalyst systems may be already different at the beginning of the reaction. Consequently, instead of considering the absolute fluorescence of a catalyst system at a particular point of time, we rather analyzed the relative fluorescent decay and determined the corresponding half-life through exponential curve fitting ([Table S8](#)). This approach was highly successful and reliable (see below) for gaining a rough indication of particularly effective catalysts (see champion table and associated kinetic traces in [Figures 4D](#) and [S13](#)). From the compounds tested, *N*-alkylated imidazoles and pyridines with electron-donating substituents in *meta*- or *para*-position catalyzed the hydrolysis reaction most efficiently. In particular, DMAP was found to be the catalyst giving rise to the fastest fluorescence decay ($t_{1/2} = 1.5$ min, [Table S8](#)). Besides DMAP, 27 other compounds were identified that outcompete pyridine as hydrolysis catalysts ([Table S8](#)). To ensure that the observed decrease in fluorescence intensity was, indeed, indicative of enhanced hydrolysis of acylphosphates, the most promising catalysts of [Figure 4D](#) were tested as additives in our NaphPO_4 reference system under HPLC monitoring as shown in [Figures S59–S64](#). As shown in [Figures S60](#) and [S64](#), the relatively low concentration of 10 mM DMAP was sufficient to decrease the hydrolysis half-life by a factor of 22.

Organophosphate and carboxylic anhydride scope

To evaluate whether a wide range of building blocks and fuels can be used in the acylphosphate reaction cycle, we carried out a scope study. Because DMAP was found to be an efficient acylphosphate hydrolysis agent, it was used in combination with pyridine in the reaction cycles to facilitate hydrolysis within a reasonable amount of time. As figures of merit, we determined the activation yield after 2 min for the forward reaction, i.e., how much of the organophosphate was converted to the respective acylphosphate, and the hydrolysis half-life of the backward reaction. As can be seen in [Figure 5](#) and [Table S9](#), the scope study included aromatic ([1](#), [2](#), and [5a–5c](#)), aliphatic ([3](#)), and (poly-)phosphate-based ([4](#), [6ab](#), and [7ab](#)) substrates. The overall conversion of the organophosphate substrate to the respective acylphosphate(s) proceeded in all cases nearly quantitatively. This finding suggests that the activation strategy applied herein can be used to acylate a wide range of organic phosphates. Furthermore, it is noteworthy that using 2-(phosphonoxy)benzoic acid as substrate intramolecular acylphosphate formation was achieved via transacetylation of acetic anhydride (compound [2](#)). In the case of anhydride fuels other than acetic anhydride, for solubility reasons, the reactions had to be conducted in a 1:1 mixture of DMF/ H_2O ([5a–5c](#)) and showed similar activation yields. Whereas the activation yields were comparable for the compounds shown, we observed pronounced differences in the hydrolysis half-lives. The relative susceptibility toward hydrolysis seems similar to that of carboxylic acid esters. Specifically, the hydrolysis rate increases if electron-withdrawing groups enhance the electrophilicity of the carbonyl group in the mixed anhydride. Therefore, aromatic substrates (such as [1](#) and [5a](#)) exhibit faster hydrolysis rates than their aliphatic counterparts ([3](#)) and (poly)phosphates ([4](#), [6a](#), and [7a](#)). A related trend was also observed in the double acylation of ortho- and pyrophosphates (compounds [6](#) and [7](#)). Due to charge depletion upon acylation, the hydrolysis in the 2-fold acylated state is significantly faster than in the mono-acylated state. Particularly long hydrolysis half-lives were observed for compounds [2](#), [5b](#), and [5c](#). On the one hand, this can be attributed to the fact that the reactions for compounds [5a–5c](#) were not conducted in pure aqueous medium, but instead in a DMF-water mixture (comparison of hydrolysis half-lives of [5a](#)). On the other hand, the acyl phosphates [2](#), [5b](#), and [5c](#) have sterically more demanding residues, which disfavors nucleophilic attack of the catalyst. Nevertheless, hydrolysis takes place in all cases, indicating that these fuels can be put to use in chemically driven steady states.

Figure 5. Scope study of acylphosphate reaction cycle

Activation yields were determined by quantitative ³¹P-NMR spectroscopy with TMP (10 mM) as internal standard after 2 min reaction time. Hydrolysis half-lives were obtained by fitting the exponential decay. Reaction conditions: 25 mM substrate, 100 mM anhydride, 10 mM pyridine, 10 mM DMAP, 1 M MOPS buffer, pH = 7.5, T = 25°C. Notes: the reactions of acylphosphates **5a–5c** were also conducted in DMF/H₂O 1:1 as solvent (data shown in gray). Kinetic data are shown in [Figures S65–S76](#). ^aSubstrate showed slight dephosphorylation over time. ^bSubstrate was acylated multiple times. ^cDue to the rapid hydrolysis of compound **6a**, the activation yield determined after 2 min probably deviates from the peak concentration of this species.

Conclusions

We demonstrate that acylphosphates, the mixed anhydrides of organophosphates and carboxylates, form a robust chemical reaction cycle that can be driven by carboxylic anhydride or carbodiimide fuels. A notable difference of acylphosphates as transient species when compared with carboxylic anhydrides is that, under the conditions typically used (pH 5–8), they are negatively charged, which we expect to be an advantage for the progressive operation of molecular machines. A significant benefit compared with the phosphoramidate reaction cycle described by us recently⁴⁰ is that, thanks to organocatalysis and activation on the electrophilic carbon atom, acylphosphates can be generated without accumulation of inert pyrophosphate side products. The use of pyridine catalysts also makes acylphosphate steady states highly tunable with respect to the kinetics of both the condensation and the hydrolysis reaction. Therefore, we were able to generate transient aggregates and excimers using this approach and carry out up to 25 fuel cycles, which compares favorably with the state of the art.^{28,86,87} Based on these proof-of-principle results, we believe that the non-equilibrium steady states from

acylphosphates will find further uses in molecular machines and dissipative self-assemblies. With the use of acylphosphate excimers in optical catalyst screenings, we showcase powerful methodology that we expect to be broadly useful for identifying efficient catalysts reliably and in a short amount of time.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Resource availability

Lead contact

Further information and requests for resources should be directed to and will be fulfilled by the lead contact, Max von Delius (max.vondelius@uni-ulm.de).

Materials availability

All materials generated in this study are available from the [lead contact](#) without restriction.

Data and code availability

The datasets generated during this study are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10159655>.

SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION

Supplemental information can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chempr.2023.11.015>.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Conceptualization: M.v.D. and A.E.; methodology: A.E. and F.M.; investigation: A.E. and J.L.S.; characterization and resources: A.E., F.M., A.J.C.K., and J.L.S.; writing: A.E. and M.v.D.

DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests.

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